

I. The Indian Chemical Society (1924-1932).

II. The Science of Optics in the Service of Chemistry*.

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In my last presidential address at Bangalore, I pointed out that the custom had grown which required the President to give his address on some purely scientific subject. At this anniversary meeting, I propose to make a slight departure from this practice, and to give some account of the Society as "a body politic and corporate."

I shall, therefore, divide my address into two parts. The first of these will deal with the life of the Society during the nine years of its existence. This will enable our Fellows to take stock of the progress which has been achieved since the foundation of the Society in 1924. The second part of my address will describe the services which the Science of Optics has rendered to chemistry and will contain brief comments on studies on the rotatory dispersion of organic compounds carried out at Ravenshaw College, Cuttack.

I. THE INDIAN CHEMICAL SOCIETY (1924-1932).

The Indian Chemical Society came into existence in 1924 as the result of several meetings and deliberations of chemists held at Madras (1922), Lucknow (1923) and Bangalore (1924), during the Science Congress Weeks. This gave it, from the very commencement, an All-India character, which was further guaranteed by requiring its anniversary meeting to be held in conjunction with the annual gathering of the Indian Science Congress. The latter is a peripatetic body and holds its meeting at different centres of learning. In this way it was hoped to establish personal contact between the Society and its Fellows, scattered all over India.

The Indian Chemical Society was registered as a corporate body on the 9th May, 1924. The first meeting of the Council was held on

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the 30th September, 1924, and the first ordinary meeting on the 24th November, 1924. Thus the Society now enters the tenth year of its existence. During this period it has made steady progress in the number of its Fellows and subscribers, in the number of exchange journals, in the size of its own journal and in its general financial condition. The progress achieved under these different heads can be judged from the figures given in Tables I and II.

TABLE I.

Table showing the progress of the Society during 1924-1932.

Year.	No. of Fellows.	No. of Subscribers.	No. of Exchange Journals.	No. of Pages published.	No. of Papers received.	No. of Papers Published.
1924	101	15	10	224	33	23
1925	243	64	38	449	48	44
1926	330	78	48	430	71	48
1927	340	81	54	572	75	78
1928	348	87	84	778	109	88
1929	393	98	93	1014	143	106
1930	377	102	103	950	115	113
1931	387	105	110	794	110	100
1932	360	100	116	700	114	98

The number of Fellows, which was 101 in 1924, increased in 1929 to the record figure of 393, but it fell to 360 in 1932. The number of subscribers to the journal shows a steady increase which reflects the popularity of the journal. The Society has instituted a Free list by which the journal is sent free of cost to 108 institutions. It was decided last year to raise this number to 158. The number of exchange journals now reaches the high figure of 116. In these ways it is sufficiently ensured that the original papers published in our journal get wide circulation. The size of the journal has also increased. In 1924, the number of pages printed was 224; it increased to 1014 in 1929. But owing to financial difficulties, it has not been possible to maintain the same size. On the other hand, the Society has been forced to keep it within the sanctioned limit of 750 pages, which are printed free of cost by the University of Calcutta.

The development of the journal is thus being retarded with obvious detriment to the progress of chemistry in this country. It is, however, hoped that the Society will be able to devise means to overcome these obstacles to its progress.

During the first four years of its existence (1924-27), the journal was quarterly. It was made bi-monthly during 1928-29. Since 1930, it has become a monthly publication. The change has had one beneficial result; it takes much less time now for a paper to appear than formerly.

The financial position of the Society during the period under review is shown in a tabular form, under summary of accounts (Table II).

TABLE II.

Summary of Accounts for 1924-1932.

Year.	Total Re- ceipts.	Subscriptions from		Sale proceeds.	Adver- tisement proceeds.	Dona- tions.	Expen- diture.	Balance.	Reserve Fund.*
	Rs.	Fell. Rs.	Subs- cribers. Rs.	Rs.	Rs.	Rs.	Rs.	Rs.	Rs.
1924	3,120	2,685	nil	76	50	300	1,302	1,818	nil
1925	8,075	3,005	1,084	378	512	3,048	2,607	5,468	4,500
1926	6,136	4,260	1,273	151	451	3,200	4,687	1,449	9,896
1927	7,927	4,607	979	98	509	1,600	5,913	2,014	9,896
1928	9,726	4,512	1,433	329	621	2,650	7,252	2,474	13,870
1929	10,989	5,714	1,491	419	654	2,400	8,415	2,574	15,909
1930	9,037	4,742	1,450	271	746	1,400	9,544	2,430	16,409
1931	10,534	5,352	1,500	439	1,072	1,500	9,515	2,495	19,814
1932	10,932	4,953	1,428	290	1,063	1,375	8,725	2,207	21,243

Although the expenditure of the Society has increased from Rs. 1302 in 1924 to Rs. 8415 in 1929, there has been a corresponding rise in the income of the Society during the same period. In spite of the fact that the year 1930 showed an opening balance of Rs. 2,574, the financial position of the Society

* The Special Reserve Fund of Rs. 10,000 for a Building of the Indian Chemical Society is not included in this column.

suffered a set back this year owing to the large arrears in subscriptions from Fellows, smaller number of new admissions, and a fall in the amount received from donations. This must be attributed to the general economic depression in world trade. Scientific societies in other countries have also been similarly hard hit. Another reason for an adverse balance in the income and expenditure of the Society in 1930 was that owing to the increase in the size of the journal in 1929, a large sum had to be paid to the University of Calcutta for printing 264 pages in excess of the sanctioned limit. Consequently the size of the journal has been reduced since 1931. Another unfortunate effect of this adverse state of affairs has been the discontinuance of the research grant since 1930. As a result of these drastic steps, the position of the Society has been again rendered solvent. The reserve fund shows a balance of Rs. 21,243, there being also a special fund of Rs. 10,000 for a building for the Chemical Society.

Building for the Indian Chemical Society.

Since its inception, the Indian Chemical Society has been housed in the Science College, University of Calcutta, usually in the private room of the Honorary Secretary, who has always happened to be a Professor of this institution. With each change in the Secretary, the Society has had to shift itself from room to room. At present the office is located in one corner of the library of the Chemical Department, and is allotted a space measuring only about 12' x 10'. The office is overcrowded. The valuable exchange journals are stored away, and cannot, therefore, be consulted by our Fellows. This arrangement, which is very unsatisfactory, is only of a temporary nature and may be terminated at any time, should the needs of the Science College demand such a step. The Council of the Society has always kept itself busy in finding out a solution of this urgent problem. Our First President, Sir P. C. Rây, made a generous gift of Rs. 10,350 towards the Building Fund in 1932, and several attempts were made by the Council to secure a home for the Society. The Government of Bengal were moved to grant a lump sum towards the cost of the building, the plan and estimate of cost, asked for by Government, being duly submitted by

us. But owing to their financial difficulties, the Government of Bengal did not find themselves in a position to help us.

The Corporation of Calcutta was also approached with a view to obtain a suitable plot in the proximity of the Science College or the Presidency College, but we were informed that no such site was available. In connection with these attempts of the Council to secure a home for the Society, I should specially mention Dr. J. N. Mukherjee for his tireless efforts on our behalf. The Council of the Society made another attempt in September, 1932, towards securing a home for itself in negotiations which are still pending with the University of Calcutta. If this scheme fructifies, the University will complete the third storey of the extension of the southern wing of the Science College at an approximate cost of Rs. 10,000 and the Society will pay this sum from its Building Fund to the University on condition that in case the rooms were required by the University for its own purposes, this sum will be returned to the Indian Chemical Society. I would recommend the scheme for your warm approval, for in that case the Society will get three large rooms with a floor area of 1740 square feet, which will be sufficient for its needs for some time to come. One great advantage of the scheme is that the overhead charges for maintenance and service of these rooms would be very small.

The Council of the Indian Chemical Society.

Last year the number of ordinary members of the Council was raised to 20. The method of election to the Council and distribution of these seats among the different territorial centres of active chemical research was entrusted to a sub-committee, the report of which will be considered at this annual meeting.

Branches of the Indian Chemical Society.

On account of the great distance of active centres of chemical research from Calcutta, the headquarters of the Society, it is not usually possible for Fellows from these centres to attend more than one meeting annually, namely, the anniversary meeting, which is held in the first week of January, in conjunction with the gathering of the Indian Science Congress. For this reason

any centre of learning with forty Fellows on the rolls of the Society is entitled to the privilege of forming a branch Society. The parent Society remits 10 per cent of the subscriptions to the branch Society for its expenses. The branch Society in return submits its annual report together with a statement of accounts to the Indian Chemical Society. We have now three such branches at Lahore (7th December, 1925), Bombay (29th April, 1926) and Madras (27th March, 1929). The Lahore branch has been most successful in raising funds for several post-graduate research scholarships. Another interesting feature of this branch is its annual dinner—a very important social function—thus setting a great example in social life to the parent Society. The credit for this, among others, goes to my esteemed colleague, friend and old pupil, Dr. S. S. Bhatnagar.

Sir. P. C. Rây Jubilee Celebration.

The great Indian Savant and benefactor of the Society, Sir P. C. Rây attained his 70th birthday last year. The Council of the Society decided to celebrate this auspicious occasion by publishing a commemoration volume, containing original papers, or resumés of original work. This volume, together with an address from the Council, will be presented to Sir P. C. Rây on your behalf, as a token of the high esteem and love in which he is held by all of us.

Honorary Fellows.

The first honorary fellowship of the Society was conferred in 1929 on Prof. A. Sommerfeld of Munich, at the time of his visit to Calcutta in 1928-29. This year the same honour is to be conferred on Sir C. V. Raman, whose nomination has been unanimously recommended by the Council. I need hardly refer to the unique scientific attainments of Sir C. V. Raman which are so well known to all of you, and the outstanding distinction conferred on him by the award of the Nobel Prize for Physics for 1930, for his researches on light-scattering, which led to the discovery of the "Raman Effect," must be still fresh in your mind.

Our Requirements.

The most urgent need of the Society is money for removing our two long-felt wants. One of them relates to the permanent housing

of the Society, to which reference has already been made. The second is the provision of a whole time paid Editor of the Journal. He should possess at least the qualifications of a University Reader with sufficient emoluments to attract the best man. As time goes on, and the journal increases in size, the services of such an Editor will become almost indispensable to its efficient editing and management. I would, therefore, appeal, through you, to people of wealth to come forward with liberal contributions and endowments for these purposes.

II. THE SCIENCE OF OPTICS IN THE SERVICE OF CHEMISTRY.

I now pass on to the second part of my address. The Science of Optics has had a very intimate connection with Chemistry and its applications have rendered signal service to the growth of chemical theory. Refraction, absorption, and optical activity, both natural and magnetic, have been studied by the chemist for over a century.

Raman Effect and Infra-red Absorption.

Recently the study of light-scattering has proved of fundamental importance to the science of chemistry. This phenomenon was first observed in 1923 by Dr. Ramanathan*, working under Sir C. V. Raman¹ at Calcutta. When an optical medium (such as a gas, liquid, crystal or glassy solid) is illuminated with monochromatic light, much of the most intense part of the spectrum of the internally scattered light emerging from within the volume of the

As early as 1923, Ramanathan while working on the scattering of light in liquids, noticed that there is a feeble radiation emitted by even the most carefully purified liquids, the wave-length of which is not the same as that of the incident light. This was at first mistaken for fluorescence, but it was difficult to understand why almost all liquids should persist in showing it, even after repeated purification which should remove all the fluorescent impurities. Ramanathan, therefore, described it as 'a special kind of feeble fluorescence'. It is now known that this peculiar radiation is only an aggregate effect of the well known line spectrum discovered by Sir C. V. Raman in 1928. The chief drawback in the earlier work (1923) was that a spectroscope was not made use of, and the visual observations could not reveal the existence of any discrete wave-lengths. In addition to these observations of Ramanathan, and prior to the discovery of the Raman Effect in 1928, there are numerous references to this phenomenon in several papers by Raman and his co-workers.

substance is a line in the same position as for the incident light. Along with this we have radiations of altered frequency consisting partly of new lines or bands displaced from the parent line and also, in the case of fluids, of a continuous spectrum which envelops both the parent line and the new or displaced lines appearing in the spectrum. The Raman Spectrum thus obtained is characteristic of the substance used, and moves bodily up or down the scale of frequency, when the frequency of the incident radiation is varied. It may be represented by a reversible energy-reaction between matter and radiation according to the scheme.

The scattering process involves, in general, an exchange of energy between the light quantum or photon and the molecules. If the photon loses part of its energy to the molecule, it would be scattered with a diminished frequency; on the other hand if the photon gains energy from the molecule, it is scattered with an increase of frequency.

The essential features of the Raman Effect are (a) its universality—it is observed in gases, liquids, crystals or glassy solids; (b) its spectral character; (c) its representation as interaction between matter and radiation. The frequency difference between the incident radiation and the Raman Line is independent of the wave-length of the exciting radiation, and coincides in magnitude with the infra-red absorption frequency of the molecule. In this way, Raman Effect is correlated with the infra-red absorption spectra of chemical substances, and its utility as an aid to the exploration of molecular spectra, especially in the infra-red, is obvious. It is therefore, of great value in elucidating the shape, size and structure of molecules. The method of light scattering is, however, much more convenient and accurate to work with than the study of infra-red absorption with its experimental technique which is particularly difficult. The remote regions of the infra-red spectrum which are very difficult of access are made easily accessible by the Raman method. Certain inactive frequencies, not occurring in the infra-red absorption, appear very strongly in the Raman Spectrum. On the other hand, the fundamental modes of vibration of the molecule, which appear strongly

in the infra-red absorption may be extremely weak in scattering. There are thus very significant differences in the character of the two spectra. A combined study by the two methods is of the greatest importance for the elucidation of chemical constitution. The results obtained from a study of the Raman Spectrum can distinguish the nature of chemical binding, namely co-valent or electrovalent molecules. Electrovalent molecules give no lines, whereas co-valent molecules give strong Raman Lines². Accordingly compounds which give the strongest spectra in light scattering are those of carbon—the typical co-valent element.^{2^a}

As the presence of non-ionised co-valent molecules in solution can be detected from a knowledge of the Raman Spectra, its utility in the study of electrolytic dissociation is also clear.^{2^b} One of the many other interesting results arising out of the application of the Raman Spectrum is the detection of the non-homogeneity of hydrogen.³ The Raman Spectrum of liquid hydrogen indicates that this substance is a mixture of two effectively distinct set of molecules, which is in agreement with the result already obtained from measurements of the specific heat of hydrogen gas.^{3^a}

Raman Spectra being the most recent discovery in point of time, have been treated first, as they promise to provide more accurate knowledge of the structure of molecules than any other spectral method. A large amount of work is now being carried out in associating the shift of particular linkages, and as a result of this work much light is likely to be thrown on constitutive problems of complex organic compounds.

Emission and Absorption Spectra in the Visible and Ultraviolet Regions.

During the early days of spectroscopic work, the interest of the chemist lay chiefly in the assignment of many new spectra to elements and the compounds responsible for them. This was due to the pioneer investigations of Bunsen and Kirchoff, and led to important chemical discoveries, and in particular to the recognition of new elements. With improvements in experimental technique, such as the introduction of high dispersion spectroscopes, interferometers, etc., wave-length measurements were carried out more accurately, and by the year 1913, about 100,000 lines had thus been registered. Spectroscopic analysis is proving an invaluable aid to chemical analysis. On the qualitative side, its utility lies in its rapidity and

certainty. Its remarkable sensitivity is well illustrated by A. de Gramont's observation that zinc is a constituent of all animal organisms⁴. In qualitative spectroscopic analysis, the material to be examined is introduced into an arc or into a condensed spark⁵, and the spectrum is photographed with a quartz spectrograph over the wave-length range, 7,000—2,000Å. A comparison spectrum, such as that of the iron arc, is cast upon the same plate. The wave-lengths of the lines from the unknown material are measured by means of a micrometer, and are identified with known spectra by reference to standard Tables of wave-lengths⁶.

Applications of spectroscopic observations to quantitative analysis depend on indirect methods. The method of N. Lockyer⁷ is based on a comparison of the length of lines from an unknown material with the length of the same lines from a series of standards of known composition. The method of W. N. Hartley is based on his discovery (1884) that if the quantity of any element present in a material is gradually diminished to a very small value, lines due to that element successively disappear from the resulting spectrum until only a few are left. The first method is cumbersome, and the second is semi-quantitative. There is, however, a third method developed by de Gramont⁸ and by Meggers, Kiess, and Stimson,⁹ which is the most satisfactory. It utilises the intensity of the lines of the elements as a spectroscopic quantity which varies in a determinable manner with its quantity present in the sample under examination. The intensities of the lines in a spectrogram from the material are compared and matched with their intensities in a series of spectrograms taken under the same conditions from material of known composition. The spectrograms in both cases are obtained by introducing the materials as the poles of a condensed-spark apparatus, and photographing their spectra under the same conditions. The success of this method depends on the use of a standard form of apparatus, constant observing conditions, and the careful preparation of a series of comparison samples. These spectroscopic methods have great attraction for the chemist, as they surpass ordinary gravimetric methods in rapidity and precision, when dealing with abnormally small quantities of material. Numerous applications of this method have already been made, such as, the quantitative analysis of steels.¹⁰ Spectroscopic methods have also found application in industrial uses, as for example, the determination of nickel in fats.¹¹

Complex molecules which give characteristic absorption spectra have also been brought within the scope of the spectroscope by utilising the same principle as that employed for emission spectra by de Gramont, *i.e.*, comparison with a series of standards. The introduction of the spectrophotometer has, however, rendered unnecessary this tedious preparation of standards.

Ever since the pioneer investigations of Hartley and Huntingdon in 1879 on the spectra of liquids and solutions, absorption curves have been widely used in elucidating the structure of organic compounds.¹² Latterly these investigations have been made for the solutions of the problems of valency. From a careful study of the absorption spectra of an acid, its salt and its ester, it is shown that the ionic bond in salts gives a different spectrum from that of the non-ionic bond of the ester.^{12a}

*The Optical Rotatory Dispersion.*¹³

The phenomenon of rotatory polarisation depends on the property which certain substances possess of taking a beam of plane polarised light, and imparting a twist to the plane of polarisation: the plane polarised beam of light enters with all its vibrations compressed, say, in a vertical plane; it emerges with its vibrations which are no longer vertical, but are inclined to the right or to the left. The phenomenon of optical activity was discovered by Arago¹⁴ in 1811 in the case of quartz, by Biot¹⁵ in 1815 in the case of organic compounds, and by Faraday¹⁶ in 1846 in the case of substances subjected to the influence of a magnetic field. The importance of this discovery to the chemist has been far reaching. Biot's pioneer work on the optical activity of organic compounds led to the discovery of molecular dissymmetry by Pasteur, and the theory of molecular dissymmetry in its turn has proved of immense value in the elucidation of molecular structure of chemical compounds. In this way, the services rendered by the polarimeter have been as notable as the results obtained with the help of the spectroscope.

Soon after the discovery of the phenomenon of rotatory polarisation, the first attempt to determine the mathematical form of the curves of the rotatory dispersion of quartz was made in 1817 by Biot,¹⁷ who showed that the rotatory power was inversely proportional to the square of the wave-length, so that $\alpha = k/\lambda^2$ or $\alpha\lambda^2 = \text{constant}$. This equation was verified by plotting the thickness of quartz required to produce a rotation of 90°, 180°, 270°, etc.,

against the square of the wave-length of the light. It is noteworthy that Biot arrived at this Law of Inverse Squares, inspite of the fact that he had no source of monochromatic light, and that his only wave-lengths were Newton's values. Notwithstanding the poor facilities in experimental technique available at that time, Biot always included measurements of rotatory dispersion in his work on optically active substances. He further proceeded to apply this law to those liquids in which he had also discovered the property of optical activity, *e.g.*, oil of turpentine and an aqueous solution of cane sugar. The method adopted was to balance the rotation of the liquid against that of a quartz plate of opposite sign. In each case the compensation appeared to be exact, which proves that the law of inverse squares held equally for the liquids as for the rock crystal. It was not, however, long before it was recognised that the law of inverse squares was not exact and universally true. Biot himself from the first had suspected small deviations; in 1836 he obtained definite evidence of this fact when trying to compensate *laevo*-rotatory turpentine against a *dextro*-rotatory oil of lemon, either in separate tubes, or mixed, and was led to observe that "the compensation of the deviations, although very close for all the rays, was, however, neither complete nor general"¹⁸. Even the approximation to Biot's law, which had been found to hold good for all substances hitherto studied, disappeared in the case of aqueous solutions of tartaric acid. They were found to obey a totally different law, since the rotatory power of the acid, instead of increasing progressively as the wave-length of the light diminished, passed through a maximum in the green region of the spectrum.¹⁹ Biot was thus led to divide optically active substances into two groups: (i) those which obeyed approximately the law of inverse squares, (ii) those which did not obey it, *e.g.*, tartaric acid. After Biot's death, on account of increased accuracy in polarimetric work, deviations from the law of inverse squares became too marked to be ignored, and led to its general abandonment even as a first approximation. Several other formulæ were, however, put forward as expressions connecting rotatory power with wave-length, such as those by von Lang and Stefan,²⁰ $\alpha = A + B/\lambda^2$; by Boltzmann²¹, $\alpha = A/\lambda^2 + B/\lambda^4$, and by Lommel²², $\alpha = k\lambda^2/(\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2)^2$. These formulæ, being empirical, proved of little value and broke down under more stringent experimental conditions. As a result of this, interest in the study of rotatory dispersion diminished. The dis-

covery of the Bunsen burner in 1866 made it easy to produce the D-line of the sodium flame which acquired almost a monopoly as a source of light for polarimetric measurements. This was fatal to the study of rotatory dispersion, since no other monochromatic light could be produced with equal ease. Organic chemists became accustomed to determine the rotatory power of the ever increasing number of optically active compounds for the sodium doublet only; this was pardonable in their case for lack of experimental technique. There was, however, no justification for the physical chemists, seeking to discover the influence of solvent, concentration, temperature, or chemical constitution on rotatory power to work with sodium light only and to record a single point on the curve of rotatory dispersion of unknown form. This work has met with little success, as the effects produced by variation of temperature, or by dilution with different solvents so complex that no simple rules have been discovered. The influence of the wave-length of the light is, however, simpler and should be studied for two reasons. In the first place, it is of no use to seek to establish fundamental laws with the help of measurements which are restricted to only one wave-length. The form of the dispersion curve should be determined. Secondly, the effect of change of wave-length on rotatory power is not accompanied by any change in the medium, whereas changes of temperature, solvent and concentration may introduce complications by altering the structure of the molecule. These considerations demand the study of dispersion as a preliminary to all investigations on optical activity, with a view to determine the type to which the dispersion curve of the material under examination belongs.

The study of rotatory dispersion has been of great value in another direction also. It has provided us with a new method for distinguishing isomeric, tautomeric and polymeric from polymorphic optically active substances.²³

Experimental Methods of Measuring Rotatory Dispersion in the Different Regions of the Spectrum.

Rotatory Dispersion in the Visible Region.—The experimental determination of rotatory dispersion in the visible region has been rendered easy by the introduction of new sources of light, such as the enclosed mercury and cadmium²⁴ arc-lamps as well as the

cadmium-silver arc burning between a vertical and a horizontal electrode. Additional lines of sodium and lithium are rendered available by suitably introducing salts of these metals into the carbon arc. The spectra of these metals are so simple that no elaborate purification is required. A direct vision prism on the eye-piece as employed by Perkin²⁵ is sufficient to read these lines and avoid the presence of stray light. A wide slit opening symmetrically in front of the triple-field is the only other modification which has to be made in adapting an ordinary polarimeter for measurements of rotatory dispersion. The routine measurements are carried out for about 10 wave-lengths distributed along the visible spectrum as follows:

Li	Cd	Li	Na	Hg	Hg	Ag	Cd	Cd	Hg
6708	6438	6104	5893	5781	5461	5209	5086	4800	4358
Red		Orange	Yellow		Green			Blue	Violet

If additional lines are required, they can be easily obtained from the line spectra of copper, zinc (in the form of brass) and silver. But on account of the greater complexity of these spectra, it is necessary to narrow down the triple-field of the polarimeter by means of the slit in order to prevent overlapping, and to illuminate the polarimeter by light which has already passed through a spectroscope before being thrown into the triple-field. These additional lines are as follows:²⁶

Zn	Cu	Cu	Ag	Ag	Cu	Cu	Cu	Zn	Zn	Zn
6362	5782	5700	5472	5465	5218	5153	5106	4810	4722	4680
Red	Yellow		Green				Blue			

Rotatory Dispersion in the Ultraviolet Region.—The study of the rotatory dispersion in the ultraviolet region has assumed great importance, as it is especially in this region that the essential characters of the dispersion curves are first disclosed. Several photographic methods have been used at different times. The method of Joubin²⁷ is now only of historical interest. The method of Nutting²⁸ was a notable advance in the technique of rotatory dispersion work. From the measurements of the displacement of fringes for each spectral ray, the rotatory power is calculated. The relative error in this method is, however, very

great. In the other methods which have been used, the complete extinction of a single field is replaced by that of two or three contiguous fields of different intensities. On one side of the extinction, one of the fields is very dark, while the other is bright ; reverse is the case on the other side ; whilst between these two extreme positions there is equality of intensity of the different fields which corresponds to complete extinction. It is indicated by an abrupt change in the intensity of illumination of the different portions of the field. These methods arranged chronologically are those of St. Landau,²⁹ Lowry,³⁰ Darmois,³¹ and Kuhn.³² The method of Lowry is very precise and allows any accidental displacement of the apparatus to be disclosed by the inequality of illumination of the exterior fields. In this method an iron-arc is used as a source of illumination, and the telescope of the analyser is replaced by a long-focus lens, by means of which a real image of the triple field is thrown on to the slit of the spectrograph. The spectrum which is formed in the spectrograph is divided into three horizontal strips corresponding to the three portions of the triple field, and measurements of the rotatory power are made by observing the wave-length at which the three divisions of the spectrum lines are equally bright for a given setting of the analyser. For lower down the ultraviolet region, the Nicol prisms are replaced by Foucault prisms and for still lower wave lengths, all the calcite must be eliminated from the apparatus, *e.g.*, by replacing the Foucault by Rochon prisms, and the quartz-calcite lenses by quartz or quartz-fluorite.

The instruments of Landau, Darmois and Lowry require trial and error to find out the rotations through an extended spectral interval, especially when multiple line-spectra are used. This is eliminated in the apparatus of Cotton and Descamps.³³ Their instrument is based on the principle that the rotatory movement of the analyser produces a displacement of the image recorded on the sensitised plate. Light which has passed through the polariser, and a trough containing the liquid and the analyser, along an axis $x x$, is deflected at right angles to this axis by a train of prisms. It falls on a photographic film bent into a cylindrical form with $x x$ as the axis of the cylinder, forming upon it a series of images of a short slit for the different ultraviolet lines of the mercury arc-lamp employed for illumination. The analyser and the train of prisms are mounted together, so that they form a system which can be rotated

about the $x x$ axis. The light spots move over the photographic plate, which registers their intensities for different positions of the analyser, making it possible to determine the angle at which each of them is extinguished. In the instrument as constructed, the first prism of the train also acts as the analyser, being made of Iceland spar; the second prism is of quartz, and the necessary lenses and the trough walls are transparent to ultraviolet rays. The rotatory dispersion is determined by giving two exposures, the first in the absence of the active substance, and the second with the latter in the apparatus. The first film records the extinctions which are produced for all the lines simultaneously (polarimetric zero); the second film gives the extinctions for the active substance. The exact positions of the extinctions on the negatives are deduced from a study of the photographic density of the images by means of the reading microphotometer of Challenge and Lambert.³⁴

Rotatory Dispersion in the Infra-red Region of the Spectrum.

The infra-red measurements are made with a triplefield polarimeter having Nicol prisms of large aperture.³⁵ The light from a Nernst lamp is focussed through this apparatus on the slit of the infra-red spectrometer, having a sensitive thermopile fitted in the focus of the eye-piece of the telescope. The intensity of the transmitted radiations is measured by means of the galvanometer deflections for different settings of the drum of the spectrometer. Work in the infra-red region is difficult not only on account of the increasing weakness of the radiation, but also on account of the extremely low rotatory power,

Types of Rotatory Dispersion.

Although Biot had discovered the law of inverse squares in 1817, and the errors in the law in 1836 as already remarked, the experimental data on rotatory dispersion at his disposal were not sufficiently accurate to enable him to correct the law, $a = k/\lambda^2$. His graphical method of plotting $1/a$ against λ^2 , which he had employed in testing the law, would have shown that the straight line does not pass through the origin at $\lambda^2 = 0$, but intersects the axis of zero rotation at a finite distance from the origin, *i. e.*, at a point given by $\lambda^2 = \lambda_0^2$. The true law of rotatory dispersion then becomes $a = k/(\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2)$, instead of $a = k/\lambda^2$. In 1898, Drude³⁶ as the result of a long

theoretical investigation, based on the electronic theory of radiation, first enunciated the law of rotatory dispersion in the general form

$$\alpha = \frac{k}{\lambda^2} \sum \frac{\theta_h f'_h N_h}{1 - \frac{\tau_h}{T}} = \frac{k_n}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_n^2} \text{ (approximately),}$$

where the "dispersion constants" λ_n^2 , corresponding with the natural free periods $1/\lambda_n$ of the electrons, were deduced from measurements of the refractive dispersion, according to the equation,

$$N^2 = E + \sum \frac{M_n}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_n^2}$$

in which N is the refractive index, and E is the dielectric constant of the medium. The generalised formula of rotatory dispersion did not find any application for many years, except in the solitary case of quartz by Drude himself as a two-term equation. The reason for this is not far to seek. Although a vast number of optically active substances were prepared and studied, the rotatory power of a great majority of them had been determined for one wavelength only. Lowry³⁷ for the first time in 1913 showed that the single term of Drude's equation, involving only two arbitrary constants, namely, a "rotation constant" and a "dispersion constant" λ_0^2 , as set out in the equation $\alpha = k/(\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2)$, was sufficient to express the rotatory dispersion of a large number of secondary alcohols of the aliphatic series. Further applications of Drude's simple formula were made by him³⁸ with about 37 compounds of the terpene series for which Rupe³⁹ had published in 1915 a series of measurements of the rotatory power for four different wavelengths.

Simple and Complex Dispersion.

As a result of this work, Lowry⁴⁰ has classified rotatory dispersions as "simple" or "complex," according as they can or cannot be expressed by the equation, $\alpha = k/(\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2)$. This equation which differs from Biot's equation only by the addition of the constant λ_0^2 was deduced by Drude for rotatory dispersion in transparent media; it does not, therefore, apply to the absorbent media studied by Cotton⁴¹ where anomalies are observed on passing through the region of absorption.

Examples of Simple Dispersion.

This simple formula is valid for a large number of secondary alcohols³⁷ and for nicotine⁴² containing a single asymmetric carbon atom. It is also valid for methylcyclohexylideneacetic acid⁴³ which contains no asymmetric carbon atom. Other substances which obey the simple dispersion law are camphorquinones, oxymethylenecamphors⁴⁵ and their condensation products with aromatic amino compounds,⁴⁶ the rotatory dispersion of which has been investigated by the present writer. An inspection of the structural formulæ of these compounds, which contain two, four or six asymmetric carbon atoms, reveals the fact that they are complex ring compounds loaded with double bonds. Sucrose^{46a} containing nine asymmetric carbon atoms, also shows simple rotatory dispersion. It is evident from these examples that the type of rotatory dispersion which a substance exhibits depends neither on its molecular structure, nor on the number of asymmetric centres which it may contain. These researches on the optical rotatory dispersion of organic compounds carry us back to the classical postulate of Molecular Dissymmetry of Pasteur, who attributed rotatory power to the dissymmetry of the whole molecule rather than to the presence of one or more asymmetric carbon atoms in it.

Examples of Complex Dispersion.

The rotatory dispersion of camphor and of most of its derivatives cannot be expressed by the equation, $\alpha = k/(\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2)$; it is therefore, not simple but complex. In nearly every case, however, it can be expressed by using two terms of Drude's equation,⁴⁷ although the dispersions are normal as in the case of camphor itself (where the rotations are positive) and sometimes anomalous as in the case of α' -bromocamphor, the dispersion curve of which shows all the three characteristic anomalies, namely, an inflexion at 5455 Å.U., a maximum at 4710 Å.U. and a reversal of sign at 3890 Å.U. Another example of anomalous rotatory dispersion, observed by the present writer, is the monoacetyl derivative of *p*-phenylenebis-aminocamphor⁴⁸. The rotatory dispersion curve of this substance in pyridine solution cuts the axis of zero rotation between the mercury green and violet regions of the spectrum, and thus exhibits one of the three characteristic anomalies, namely, reversal of sign.

Anomalous Rotatory Dispersion.

The small correction which is needed to convert Biot's law into the Law of Simple Rotatory Dispersion is of great importance, since if all optically active substances obeyed the Law of Inverse Squares, all rotatory dispersions would be normal and would be identical *e.g.*,

$$\alpha_{4358}/\alpha_{5464} = \frac{(5464)^2}{(4358)^2} = 1.52$$

In this case no form of anomalous rotatory dispersion could exist. The introduction of a second term into the equation of the rotatory dispersion gives rise to complex rotatory dispersion, and the two-term formula may be written thus

$$\alpha = \frac{k_1}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_1^2} + \frac{k_2}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_2^2}.$$

The examination of this equation discloses the fact that α is a maximum at the wave-length λ , *i.e.*, anomalous dispersion can occur, if

$$\frac{k_1}{k_2} = \frac{(\lambda^2 - \lambda_1^2)^2}{(\lambda^2 - \lambda_2^2)^2}$$

a condition which can be fulfilled when k_1 and k_2 are of opposite sign, and $k_2 > k_1$, when $\lambda_1 > \lambda_2$. From the chemical point of view, this anomaly expressed by the two-term formula is due to the presence in the liquid of two kinds of optically active molecules, possessing normal rotations of opposite sign and of unequal dispersion. This suggestion is due to Biot⁴⁸ who in 1836 produced this anomaly artificially by two methods when he attempted to compensate the optical rotatory power of *laevo*-rotatory turpentine by balancing it against a column of *dextro*-rotatory oil of lemon, in which the superposition is entirely optical, or by mixing the two liquids in suitable proportions.

The anomalous rotatory dispersion of tartaric acid was explained by Arndtsen⁴⁹ in 1858 as due to the presence of two interconvertible forms of the acid, which, however, have never been isolated. It is for this reason that special interest attaches to the work of Austin

and Park⁵⁰ on the rotatory dispersion of *laevo*-rotatory diacetyl tartaric acid, and its *dextro*-rotatory anhydride. Both these compounds exhibit simple dispersion in dry acetone (the *dextro*-rotatory compound having smaller dispersion constant), which may be expressed by the equations :

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{20^{\circ}} = -6.508 / (\lambda^2 - 0.0833)^2 \text{ (acid),}$$

$$\left[\alpha \right]_{\lambda}^{20^{\circ}} = +18.354 / (\lambda^2 - 0.0507)^2 \text{ (anhydride).}$$

In wet acetone, the anhydride undergoes gradual hydrolysis into the corresponding acid. Since the rotations of the two compounds are opposite in sign, and their dispersion constants are of unequal magnitude, all the conditions necessary to produce anomalous dispersion are present in the solution of a mixture of the two compounds. Thus a freshly prepared solution of the anhydride in wet acetone which gave a *simple dextro-rotation* soon showed a *complex and anomalous* dispersion, owing to the development in the free acid of a negative partial rotation with a high dispersion coefficient. This *complex and anomalous* dispersion was transformed in turn into a *complex and normal* dispersion when the negative term had become predominant over the whole range of wave-lengths; and finally the solution, after complete hydrolysis shows only the *simple laevo-rotation* of the free acid.

The rotatory dispersion of certain coloured substances is always anomalous in the immediate neighbourhood of an active absorption band, namely, the absorption band which is really caused by the same radicals in the molecule that are responsible for its optical activity. In the neighbourhood of such an absorption band, Drude's simple formula does not apply owing to the fact that in deducing it, certain terms, the effect of which is appreciable only in the neighbourhood of an absorption band, are neglected. If these terms are retained, then theory leads to the result that in the neighbourhood of an absorption band, the dispersion curve after passing through a maximum, changes sign, and then passes through a second maximum of the opposite sign. The theory further requires that between the two maxima, the phenomenon of *circular dichroism* (the unequal absorption of two circularly polarised rays into which the original plane vibration can be resolved) should be observable. The double maxima and the circular dichroism at an absorption band were first

observed by Cotton⁵¹ in 1896 and the phenomenon is known as the "Cotton Effect."

The applications of the study of circular dichroism to the solution of one of the most fundamental problems in natural science namely, the realisation of a *complete asymmetric photosynthesis* affords yet another instance in which the Science of Optics has rendered great service towards the elucidation of the great riddle which has puzzled the scientists since the time of Pasteur. Starting with optically inactive materials, the synthetic products of the laboratory are always racemic compounds or externally compensated mixtures of the oppositely active antipodes. These products never show any optical activity until and unless they have been resolved by one of Pasteur's methods. The products synthesised by the living plant or animal from inactive materials, such as water, carbon dioxide, ammonia, etc., are generally endowed with optical activity, and thus present a striking contrast in this respect. The direct production of optically active substances, therefore, seemed to be the very prerogative of life. Pasteur himself was led in 1860 to believe in the deep and unbridgeable gulf between the chemistry of the living and that of dead matter. Although he modified this opinion⁵² in 1884, the vitalistic views of Japp and others⁵³ expressed as late as 1898 show the existence of the belief in the great barrier between the products of the laboratory and those of life. The products of natural synthesis by plants or animals always show the same optical activity. It is the result of a *partially asymmetric synthesis* brought about by the presence of pre-existing optically active molecules in the living cell. The realisation of a *partially asymmetric synthesis* by Marckwald and Mackenzie⁵⁴ in 1900 for the first time in the laboratory has thus brought the natural synthesis by plant or animal within the scope of chemical mechanics, having reduced it to be simply a question of relative difference in reaction velocities. These researches, however, still leave unanswered the question of the origin of the first optically active substance, the presence of which has served to guide and influence the natural syntheses, taking place in plant and animal cells during all the subsequent periods. The realisation of a *complete asymmetric synthesis*, from substances devoid of any optical activity, will be therefore a great experimental triumph. Several attempts made with the aid of photochemically sensitive asymmetric substances, showing circular dichroism, such as those by Henle and Haakh⁵⁵ in 1908, Cotton⁵⁶ in 1909 and

Jaeger⁵⁷ in 1921 proved, however, unsuccessful. Recently Kuhn and Braun⁵⁸ working with Freudenberg announced that they have obtained a positive result by making use of the procedure which had been previously indicated by Cotton. They found that the rotatory power of ethyl α -bromopropionate, $\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{CH} \cdot \text{Br} \cdot \text{COOEt}$, in alcoholic solution first increases enormously, then decreases and finally changes sign as the wave-length is decreased. From these measurements of rotatory dispersion, they inferred that the substance exhibited circular dichroism. They, therefore, exposed ethereal solutions of the corresponding racemic ester simultaneously to *dextro*- and *laevo*-circularly polarised light of $\lambda = 2800 \text{ \AA}$. The maximum rotation observed in ether was only $\pm 0.05^\circ$. Further progress in the preparation of optically active substances by the help of circularly polarised light has been recorded by Kuhn.⁵⁹ It is found that when 1.5 per cent hexane solutions of racemic dimethylamide of α -azidopropionic acid, $\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{CH} \cdot \text{N}_3 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{N} (\text{CH}_3)_2$, were partly decomposed by circularly polarised light ($\lambda = 3100 \text{ \AA}$), and the undecomposed dimethylamide subsequently isolated from the solution, active preparations which showed rotation of $+0.78^\circ$ and -1.04° were obtained. The problem is thus solved in principle, and for more complete separation two conditions should be satisfied. The first is that the racemic substance should be completely dissociated in solution, and secondly we should know the spectral region in which the circular dichroism is maximum, so as to enable us to select the radiation which would give the maximum separation. The method has the advantage that it allows the production of both the isomers.

Apart from the application of circular dichroism to the preparation of the optically active substances from purely inactive materials and without the intervention of any vital processes or agencies, its utility in the solution of other physico-chemical problems is also being recognised. The existence of circular dichroism enables us to establish a very sharp distinction between the solution of a racemate and that of a simple mixture which is inactive by external compensation⁶⁰. A study of circular dichroism also allows us to throw light on the nature of the chemical bond. Whenever a liquid shows circular dichroism, it is certain that it contains molecules which are active and at the same time absorbent. Lifschitz⁶⁰ from a study of some complex derivatives of cobalt has been able to recognise in them two components one active (*i.e.*, containing an asymmetric

carbon atom) and the other absorbent (*i.e.*, a coloured ion). He distinguishes between the case in which the two components are linked by a principal valency bond, and that in which they are united by an electro-valent bond. It is only in the former case that circular dichroism would be manifest; in the other case, in which the linking between the components is electrovalent, no influence of absorption on the optical activity of the dissolved substance would be observed.

The application of other branches of Optics, such as X-ray methods, has yielded important results, and has led to definite advances in our knowledge of crystal structure, but enough has been said to show the immense debt which chemistry owes to the Science of Optics.

In concluding this address, I would like to make some suggestions which may prove useful to our young chemists during the period of their university studies. Most of the easy problems in Chemistry have been solved, and what remains to be accomplished is difficult. It is, therefore, necessary that the future investigators in chemistry should be properly trained in the fundamental Sciences, namely, Mathematics and Physics. If their work is to lie in Bio-chemistry, they should pay special attention to Biology and Physiology. Above all, skill in experimental technique is of the utmost value. As most of the original work in Chemistry is published in English, French and German, a good working knowledge of these languages should be the first preliminary preparation for all such studies. If the Indian chemists are thus equipped, we may certainly hope to see as great advances made in Chemistry in this country as have already been accomplished in Physics. The Indian mind, on account of its great development during the long period of civilisation it has witnessed, is eminently fitted for scientific investigation. What is needed is proper equipment of the workers with the necessary tools for the task before them, and when this is done, fundamental discoveries are sure to follow.

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